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A CASE REPORT: PRE INFANTILE TREMOR SYNDROME WITH SEVERE ANEMIA SECONDARY TO BLOOD LOSS IN CONGESTIVE CARDIAC FAILURE.

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ABSTRACT

Infantile tremor syndrome (ITS) is a rare clinical disorder characterized by clinical syndrome coarse tremors, anaemia and regression of motor acute or gradual onset of mental and psychomotor changes; pigmentation disturbances of hair and skin, pallor, mental milestones in children of around between 5 months to 3 years of age. Exact incidence is not known. The disorder is common in exclusively breast fed infant of vegetarian mothers most of the children eventually recover but are frequently left with cognitive, language, neurodeficits and death which is associated with some life threatening disease or condition this as review attempt to provide comprehensive and up to date information on the subject. Here, an 11-month-old boy with normal development who was born to a non-consanguineous marriage was taken to the hospital with the main complaint of creeping fever since two days' worth of loose stools eight to ten times per day and three to four episodes of vomiting. On investigation Head to toe had an open anterior font, sparse hair, and hyper pigmented knuckles on the upper limbs. Additionally, the red pigment on the lips and abnormally flat or broad nails were signs of pre-ITS and severe anaemia. After starting the suggested course of treatment, the symptoms considerably improved. Child was transferred to the intensive care unit (PICU) after experiencing sudden spikes in fever, passing black tarry stool, abdominal distension, and congestive cardiac failure. The child was later diagnosed as having pre-ITS septicemia and severe anaemia secondary to bleeding in the CCF.

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INTRODUCTION

Infantile tremor syndrome (ITS) is a clinical syndrome of acute or gradual onset of mental and psychomotor changes, pigmentary disturbances of hair and skin, pallor, and tremors in malnourished children age difference between 5 months to 3 years.^[3] Vitamin B₁₂ deficiency has been found to be associated with ITS in many studies there are case reports that suggesting zinc and Vitamin C deficiency associated with ITS.^[2] As per clinical features there are 3 stage of ITS have been described on the basis of history, physical examinations and follow-up. Pre-Tremor-neuromotor Regressions, pallor and tremorous voice have been characterised. Tremor-Tremor phase appearing with sudden onset of tremor including various parts of body mainly extremities of hand and feet and Post Tremor: - In which limbs muscle are usually flabby to feel, and the presence of extra pyramidal type of rigidity on passive movements.^[1] Symptoms include bleating goat like cry, brown scanty hair, lethargy and other body site hyperpigmentation usually due to Vitamin A, D, C and B₁₂ deficiency, magnesium deficiency and infections. The low levels of vitamin B12 and its transport protein Transcobalamin II (TC II) in the cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) may be responsible for the neurological features of this syndrome.^[2-4] The presence of tremors in ITS has been attributed to structural and functional alterations of extrapyramidal system, but neuroimaging with computed tomography scan and magnetic resonance imaging suggests nonspecific structural changes. The exact incidence of ITS is not known. In India, it accounts for 0.2% -2% of paediatric hospital admissions (1%-2% in 1960s, 1.1% in 1975-77 and 0.2% in mid-1990s. 7 with the improvement in the living standard and nutritional status of the society.^[3] High protein diet, multivitamins, folic acid, iron, calcium, zinc and magnesium has been the choice of treatment for nutritional deficient individuals.^[4]

OBJECTIVE

An inpatient study at the Paediatric Department of the Karnataka Institute of Medical Sciences (KIMS) Hospital in Hubballi was carried out. The institutional ethical committee gave its approval for the case report and granted permission to gather data. This study demonstrates the potential need for multivitamin therapy, particularly high dosages of vitamin B12, as well as vitamin C, iron, protein, zinc, and magnesium supplements. Phenobarbitone (3-5 mg/kg/day) may be needed to lessen the severity and frequency of the tremors if they are severe. The administration of supportive therapy is crucial for ITS.

CASE REPORT

An 11 months old baby admitted to hospital who is developmentally normal male baby born to a non-consanguineously married couple. Patient history revealed that there is no such pervious hospitalization and similar complaints in past or family history who is consuming diet deficit of 300kcal and Development history (fine motor, gross motor language, social) milestone were up to date at the time of hospitalization, immunized till date was brought with the chief complaint of loose stools 8 to 10 episodes per day, vomiting 3 to 4 episodes and insidious fever since two days. Child is Irritable, vitals were normal with pallor in the eyes PR: 156bpm, Pulse volume: Good Peripheries: warm, RR: 42cycles per minute, SPO₂: 97% RA, Temp 100.8°F, Wiegth-8.6kg, Height 75cm.

Head to toe examination had open anterior font anellesparse hair with upper limb knuckle hyperpigmentation (Figure 1) with present Nails pallor- Anthropometry platynychia (Figure 2) and red pigmented lip (Figure 3).

Systemic examination: PA: soft non tender, umbilicus center inverted four quadrants move equally with respiration with Liver palpable liver span 7 cm spleen not palpable CVS: precordium normal, S1 S2 heard, no murmurs, Apex beat felt at left fifth intercostal space RS: Trachea central, NVBS heard, no added sounds CNS: child is irritable, No signs of meningeal irritation Sensory intact was appropriate.

Investigations were sent and diagnosed shown in (Table 1) to be a case of acute gastroenteritis with some dehydration with pre ITS with Anaemia not in failure stool microscopy was negative and child was started treatment with ORS plan B with injection ceftriaxone and vitamin B₁₂ was given intravenous for 7 days later child had spikes of fever with history of the passage of black tarry stool seen abdominal distension and stool for occult blood positive (Malena), with distress and congestive cardiac failure child was shifted to PICU with diagnosed to be Pre ITS with septicaemia with severe anaemia secondary to bleeding in CCF With severe septicaemia in DIC (Disseminated intravascular coagulation) after discussing case with staff.

Antibiotics were upgraded to Meropenam with IV fluids (4mg/kg/day), Inj. Piperacillin (100mg/kg/day) IV (TID); Inj. Vitamin K 5 mg IV-OD; Inj. Rantac 0.2cc IV BID, Inj. Lasix (0-1 ml/kg/dose) IV stat; CBC reports showed a drop in Hb (4.1gm) were PRBC transfused at 5ml /kg over 6 hr and FFP transfusion was done. where connected to the (High flow Nasal Cannula O₂) HFNC because he developed increased respiratory distress which is known as (tachypnoea/Nasal flaring), Over course of PICU stay child improved and vitals were stable with anemia not in failure and child was shifted back to step down and Child was started with F75 feeds orally as the child was not tolerating feeds and was having abdominal distension were volume was reduced and frequency was increased on day 5 of step down stay child threw generalised tonic-clonic convulsions with severe aspiration and child was taken back to PICU and child was intubated in view of distress as the child had bradycardia CPR was began and couldn't not be reviewed. According to the condition a standard treatment has followed and due to the various life threatening condition child was declared as dead.

Figure 1: Upper Limb Knuckle Hyper Pigmentation.

Figure 2: Anthropometry platynchia.

Figure 3: Red Pigmented Lip.

Table 1: Haematological investigations.

Test parameters	Pre-treatment values	On-going treatment values	Reference value
Neutrophils	20	28	40-75%
Lymphocytes	74	68	25-40%
Monocytes	2.8	2	2-8%
WBC	4.4	4.6	4.5-11.0 × 10 ⁹ /L
RBC	3.47	3.6	3.8-4.8million
HB	4.0	5.0	1.6-14%
PCT	0.32	0.19	0.108-0.282%
MCV	73.2	84	80-100f
MCH	22.4	27.1	27-32pg
MCHC	30.7	32.3	31.5-34.5%
Platelet count	3.10	3.15	1.5-4lakhs
ESR	140	-	5-20mm 1 st hr
RDW	74.8	33.3	11.6-14%
Reticulocyte production index	1%	2%	0.5-2.5%

DISCUSSION

Infantile Tremor syndrome is a rare clinical disorder, although the exact incidence data is not known, but according to the hospital statistics it has revealed that 15-10% of paediatric ward admission to be due to this disorder.^[5] The incidence has been reported decreasing trend in most geographical areas, but still isolated cases are being reported from India. As per the feeding pattern, children with ITS have been reported on breastfeeding alone with poor complimentary feeds and are breast fed by strict vegetarian mothers Even if some mothers were taking a non-vegetarian diet, that was insufficient in quantity. Despite the exact role is still to be confirmed a poor complimentary feeding and strict vegetarianism of mothers may contribute to etiology of ITS.

ITS is hypothesized that is associated with certain infection. Many children have been identified with some sort of infection preceding the onset of tremor like gastro intestinal, Fever, respiratory tract infection, wild hepatomegaly and splenomegaly is reported sign in ITS. Other illness may affected the Counts of leukocyte count bone marrow finding have predominantly normoblastic through dimorphic to megaloblastic anaemia. Under-nutrition is one of the cause of ITS and many studies found serum magnesium, serum albumin, and zinc deficiency has been reported. Vitamin B₁₂, folic A. Iron deficiency was thought to be associated with ITS which is sometime known as vitamin B₁₂ deficiency syndrome.^[2]

Brain biopsy of ITS cases found presence of inflammatory changes in meninges, Astrocytosis, along with perivascular cuffing which lead to a possibility of a probable viral agent as the cause of ITS¹ through CCF (2° to Blood loss) to severe anaemia has also been reported, whereas anaemia is always present in ITS infants.^[4] Laboratory finding of study of LFT's and RFT's (biochemistry for serum sodium, potassium chloride, Blood urea, Sugar, AST, ALT and liver) biopsies detected no abnormalities in these tests.

Vitamin B₁₂ by existing strong epidemiological clinical and laboratory evidence in favour of vitamin B₁₂ deficiency as the cause of ITS.⁴ Therapeutic dose of 50 – 100µg / dose, which shows the tremors disappeared in 1-2 weeks who received this dose of 100µg/day or 4 weeks -1 month who received 50µg/day and also improved in symptoms of haematological and Neurological. Overall impression of children diagnosed with ITS can be described as a clinical state characterised by tremor in the form of coarse, twitching of the angles, eyelids, tongue with a tremulous cry Resembling the bleating of a lamb, tossing movement of the head, wriggling and movement Of the trunk.

Infants have been reported with glossitis, angular cheilitis, edema and scurry.^[1] Treatment consist of therapy for anaemia and nutritional deficiency. Vitamin B₁₂ in high doses may be required if B₁₂ level are low. Multivitamin vitamin C, Iron, protein, zinc and magnesium supplement may also be necessary. If the tremor are severe, phenobarbitone (3-5 mg/kg/day) may be required to decrease the intensity. The tremor subside slowly. Initially there is gradual reduction in the amplitude and severity, then the tremor become intermittent and finally stop. Propranolol and chlorpromazine all other drugs, which can be used to control tremor Supportive care in the form intravenous fluids to treat and prevent dehydration, antibiotics⁴ injection meropenam is given for bacterial infection and other medications Inj. Lasix, Inj. Rantac, Inj. Piperacillin and Inj. Vitamin K to treat associated complication.

CONCLUSION

ITS needs to be considered in any child <3 years presenting with anaemia, developmental delay/regressions, skin depigmentation and sparse hair, with or without tremors. ITS typically reported in families with poor socio economic status where mother are often vegetarian and are deprived of proper balanced nutritional diet. For thorough care of ITS, multivitamin therapy especially vitamin B12 treatment of other related nutritional deficiencies, as well as supportive therapy, are crucial. To prevent long-term cognitive impairment, early detection and treatment are necessary.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

ABBREVIATIONS

ITS : Infantile tremor syndrome;
RBC : Red Blood Cell;
Hb : Haemoglobin;
PCV : Packed Cell Volume;
MCV : Mean Corpuscular Volume;
MCH : Mean Corpuscular Haemoglobin;
MCHC : Mean Corpuscular Haemoglobin Concentration;
CBC : Complete Blood Count;
INJ : Injection.

REFERENCES

1. Rajesh gupta, Ak rawat, Poonam Singh, Jyoti Gupta, Ashish Pathak. Infantile Tremor Syndrome: Current perspectives. Research and Report in Tropical Medicine. 2019; 10:103-108.
2. Col RG Holla (Retd), Col AN Prasad. Infantile Tremor Syndrome. MJAFI 2010; (66):186-187.
3. Jatinder Singh Goraya, Sukhjot Kaur. Infantile Tremor Syndrome: A review and critical appraisal of its etiology. J Pediatr Neurosci 2016 ;(11):298-304.
4. Syed Zia Inamdar, Purnagopinath, Vijaya Kumari, Sunanda Nandikol, Sushilkumar Londe, et al. Infantile Tremor Syndrome: A Case Report. Indian Journal of Pharmacy Practice, vol 15, issue 1, jan-mar 2022.
5. Datta K, Datta S, Dutta I. Rare association of central pontine myelinolysis with infantile tremor syndrome. Ann Indian Acad Neurol 2012; 15:48-50.

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